

EXPRESSIONS OF THE POLITENESS OF COMMITTING AN ACTION IN THE ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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In our everyday communication, we not only exchange information but also have to convey our attitude towards, or opinions about, the content of what we say. As such, interactants have to know how to use language to encode and decode each other's feelings and commitments to the event or the act uttered. These expressions used to reveal the Speaker's view in the utterance are identified as modality category. (House & Kasper, 1981).

Modality has mostly been considered under the umbrella of "modal auxiliaries" (Coates, 1983) or "a system of modal verbs" (Palmer 1986, 1990). Simon-Vandenberg and Aijmer (2007: 2) also claim that "modality in English has tended

ABSTRACT

This study investigates modality category used as expressions of politeness in English and Karakalpak. Results of the research reflect the semantic and pragmatic perspectives of modal verbs on the theories of modality and politeness. This research examines the relation of modality to politeness via the use of English and Karakalpak committing an action speeches. The analyses of modals as particular politeness strategies revealed that there is a close relation between politeness and modality.

to be regarded as identical with the modal auxiliaries". Accordingly, the basic assumption underlying this study is whether the general tendency of decline in the frequency of modal auxiliaries has caused any influence in the occurrence as politeness expressions in samples of committing an action speeches.

This article focuses on examining differences between the English and the Karakalpak language in the use of modal auxiliaries as politeness expressions in their speeches.

The meaning of the possibility to perform an action is conveyed by the modal verbs can - could, may-might.

"May," "might," and "could" can all be used to say that something is possible, as in "The story may/might/could be true" or "The painting may/might/could be very old." You can use any of the three in contexts like these.

"May" and "might" can both be used to say that one thing is true but that something else is also true, as in "This car may/might be more expensive than the other cars, but it will be cheaper to maintain."

The verb "can" in the form of the present tense is used with the non-perfected

infinitive of the semantic verb (without the particle to) in the real or passive voice.

The verb **can**, in the sense of being able to perform an action, has the following meaning:

1. The possibility of committing an action due to the presence of conditions for its

commission in the present or future.

I wrote to them last week. They can get me a job, and I can stay with them. - ...olar meni jumis penen ta'miynley aladi ha'm men olar menen qala alaman.

In the Karakalpak language, the verb **can** in this meaning with the infinitive

corresponds to the combination of the verb "qila aliw" in the present tense form

("qila alaman", "qila aladi", "qila alamiz") with the infinitive semantic verb.

In the negative sentence, the verb **can** expresses the impossibility of committing an

action due to the absence of appropriate conditions:

That's all over. The old days can never come back. - ... hesh qashan qaytip kelmeydi.

"whatever happened", she said, "there can be no blame on you. You were not here." - ... sizdi ayiplay almaydi.

The verb **can** with a negation in the Karakalpak language corresponds to the present tense forms of the verb "qila aliw" with denial ("qila almaydi") or forms cannot do.

In interrogative and exclamatory sentences, the verb can give a hint of doubt to the possibility of performing an action or being surprised at this action:

Ha-ha! D'ye think you can get round me this way? - ... siz meni usi jol menen alday alaman dep oylap atirsizba?

Oh, Harry, don't dislike her. She's wonderful. And besides, how you feel so

differently about someone who means so much to me! - ... qanday qilip sen bunday bola alasan'!

What you can have to say to me to do, George Harford? You can have nothing to say to me – Senin' mende ne ga'pin' bar? ... sen mağan rastan hesh nárse dey almaysañ.

The verb **can** in interrogative sentences in the Karakalpak language of the verb “qila aliw” in the form of the present tense with the words “rastan”, “rastanba”.

Verb **can** verbally can be used in subordinate clauses of the goal: *Let the dog loose, so that it can have a run. - ...ol juwira aliwi ushin...*

The verb **can** at the same time in the Karakalpak language corresponds to the

subjunctive mood of the verb “qila aliw”, and the preceding alliance is the union “ushin”.

2. The possibility of committing an action based on permission, permission, this use is typical for colloquial speech.

Form **could**. The form **could** is two-digit and may refer to the past tense and to the present. A. The use of the form **could** according to the rule of time coordination.

1. The possibility of an action due to the presence of appropriate conditions.

This was evidently proof that one species could suddenly give rise to another which could maintain it itself - ... tiykar boliwi mu'mkin.

She said only to convince him that her future could not be happy without John. - ... baxitli bola almaydi.

She wondered how Ernest could get so much enjoyment out of a newspaper . He could occupy himself with one for almost an hour . - ... sonshelli ko'p ra'ha'tleniwi mu'mkin.

2. The ability to perform an action based on permission, permission:

He wrote from Brighton asking if he could see me. - ... ol meni ko're aliwi mu'mkinligin sorap ...

In the form “can”, when used according to the rule of grading, the verb “qila aliw” in the Karakalpak language in the form of the present tense.

B. Using the form could in the context of the past tense.

1. like the form **can**, the form **could** mean the possibility of an action due to the presence of appropriate conditions:

“He could go in and see the movie and the newsreel and the comedy and go home but what good would that do him?”[Saroyan W.:1975:195]

– “Ol kiriwi, filmdi, ... ko'riwi mu'mkin edi...”

“In the next three weeks she (Fleur) found and finished a dereclit house ... with a garden and stables that could be converted easily.” – “...an'sat g'ana qaytaday o'zgeriwi mu'mkin edi”.

"Boadicea could expect no mercy from the Roman soldiers, and she killed herself with poison" - "Boadicya mehir kore almas edi..."

What could I do but go on living here? - Bul jerde jasamawim di dawam ettiriwden basqa ne qiliwim mùmkin?

In interrogative sentences, the form could express a strong surprise about the committed action and usually has an emotional tint:

Oh, Joe, how could you do it? She loved you so much, Joe, how could you do it? - qalayinsha sen bul isti qildin'?

When used in the context of past tense, **could** is used in the sub-sentence sentence;

such use could be possible not only in a spinning speech, but also in scientific literature:

2. The form **could** in the context of the past tense even express the possibility of performing an action based on a permit:

All that Winchester could do was to send its lawyer to court to see what was going on, and even so he had to pay a fee for permission to sit there. - Vinchestr qila laiwi mu'mkin bolg'an ha'mme ha'rse ...

Present tense

If the form **could** refer to the present time, then in combination with the

non -perfective infinitive, it expresses the possibility in which the speaker is not quite sure:

I could go and ask, or walk the streets or do any dirty thing easily.- Men bariwim, u'lgeriwim yaki ... mu'mkin.

"Sailed round the world in a hundred and fifty three days!" said Amos. "You could fly it now in about three." - "... siz ... usha aliwin'iz mu'mkin".

The form **could** is used with a non-defective infinitive in an interrogative sentence containing a request, which sometimes has a touch of familiarity:

E.g.: *Anson reflected: "Could you sing?" - "...siz qosiq ayta alasizba?"*

And I would say: "How do you do , Mr.Gussler? Could you make me a pair of leather boots?" - "... siz mag'an teriden bir jup etik tigip bere alasizba?"

The form **could** in the context of the present time corresponds in the Karakalpak language to the subjunctive mood of the verb "qila aliw" ("qiliwi mu'mkin edi").

In the interrogative sentences containing the request, the form **could** correspond in Karakalpak language in a polite way the combination of "qila almaysizba?"

The combination of the **could** form with the non-defective infinitive usually

expresses the possibility not implemented in the past:

Verb **may, might**

The verbs “may”, “might” have the present tense form *may* and the past tense *might*. Interrogative and negative forms are formed without the auxiliary verb: *may ... go?*

Form **may**

The verb **may**, in the form of the present tense, in the sense of the possibility of

committing an action, is used with the nonperfect infinitive of the real or passive voice without the particle “to”.

The verb **may**, in the sense of being able to perform an action, has the following shades of meaning:

1. The possibility of making an action that will be realized in the present or future,

but may not be realized:

E.g.: *Miss R. was in high spirits, just that humour for talking nonsense, which we may observe in young girls at the end of an exciting day. - ... gu'zetiwwimiz mu'kin.*

It may make that man furious. - Bul ol adamnin' ashiwin keltiriwiñ mu'mkin.

“I dare say she will get over it in time”, said Beatrice, “but it may make thing rather unpleasant for you. - ... biraq bul sizge a'dewir naxushliq keltirip shig'arishi mu'mkin.

The combination of the verb **may** in this meaning with the infinitive in the

Karakalpak language corresponds to the present tense of the verb “qiliwi mu'mkin” (“qiliwim mu'mkin, qiliwi mu'mkin, qiliwimiz mumukin”, etc.) with the infinitive.

The verb **may** is used in subordinate clauses of the goal.

E.g.: *This may be necessary in order to apply the high-speed particles. - Bul qag'iyda joqari tezliktegi bo'lekshelerge a'mel qiliniwi mu'mkin.*

2. The possibility of committing an action due to permission, permit:

E.g.: *You may give me one kiss, John. - Sen meni bir ma'rte su'yiwin' mu'mkin.*

“It was a fascinating little box today. May I have it?” - “you may little wasteful one,” said he. - Men oni alsam meylime? Meyli.

In the same meaning, the verb **may** is used in interrogative sentences containing a request or a politeness:

E.g.: *“May I give you some tea?” he said, “And won't you sit down, please?” “Sizge shay bersem meylime?...”.*

Form **might**

The form “might”, like the form “could”, can refer both to the past and to the present.

Past time

The use of the form **might** in how past tense is determined by two things:

A. The rule of the reconciliation of times

B. Just the context of the past tense.

A. The use of the form **might** by the rules of the coordination of times.

When used by agreement of times, the form **might** has the same shades of meaning as the form **may**.

1. The possibility of committing an action that may occur, but may not occur:

Still there was the risk that he might come. – Ol kelip qaliwi mu'mkin bolg'an qawip bar edi.

They feared that he might be dismissed from Yale. - ...oni bosatip jiberiliwi

mu'mkinlig'inen qorqatug'in edi.

In the Karakalpak language, the verb “mu'mkin” (“qiliwi mu'mkin, qiliwlari mu'mkin, qiliwin'iz mu'mkin”)

2. The possibility of committing an action due to the permission, permit:

He asked if he might leave the office half an hour earlier that afternoon. - ... ol jumistan yarim saat aldin ketiwge ruxst soradi.

B. Use of the **might** form in the context of past tense.

The form **might** is very rarely used as the past tense form of the verb **may**. One

example of this use of this form is its use in subordinate clauses:

He opened the long window for air and the door, that he might still hear her music drifting in. - ... onin' taralip turg'an muzikasinin' dawisin esite aliwi ushin.

The form **might** can express the possibility of permission and relating to the past tense: *The Mayor ... was provided with a fine crimson for great occasions, but he might walk up and down in his ordinary clothes outside his door about necessary business. - ... Lekin ol har dayimg'iday kiyiminde ju'riwi mu'mkin edi.* When used in conjunction with the tenses and simply in the context of the past tense, the **might** form is combined with a nonperfect infinitive.

Present tense

The form **might** also be used in the present context in combination with both non -perfective and perfect infinitive. The shape “might” has the following shades of meaning:

1. The possibility of committing an action in which the speaker is quite sure; The form **might** in this case be used with non-defective infinitive:

E.g.: You might come by the same train as Fleur – one-forty. – Sen ... keliwin' mu'mkin edi.

The combination of the form **might** in this value with the perfect infinitive

refers to the past tense and means that the possibility of performing an action in the past was not implemented:

E.g.: *It might have been a couple of orioles.* [Saroyan W.:1975:195]

– *Olar zargaldaq quslar boliwi mumkin edi.*

In your own house you might have kicked him downstairs. – ... *tewip jiberiwin'iz mu'mkin edi.*

The form “might”, in combination with both the non-perfected and the perfect

infinitive, corresponds in the Karakalpak language to the subjunctive mood forms of the verb –qiliwi mu'mkin|| (–qiliwi mu'nkin edi, islewi mu'mkin edi||)

With negation, the might form is extremely rare.

2. The possibility of taking action due to permission, permit, and the speaker is not quite sure of the implementation of this action. Usually in such a meaning, the form might is used in interrogative sentences containing the request and is combined with a non-defective infinitive:

E.g.: *Might I, fear Miss Worsley, as you are standing up, ask you for my cotton that is behind you? – ... soray almaslig'im mu'mkinbe?*

Sometimes the verb “might” at the same time conveys a shade of uncertainty, indecisiveness of the speaker: E.g.: *Might I borrow your pen for a minute? – Ruchkan'izdi bir minutqa aliwim mu'mkin emespe?*

Might I see your wife for a minute, I have a message for her? – Sizin' hayalin'izdi benen ko'rissem mu'mkinbe, ...?

The form of a might with nonperfect infinitive in an interrogative sentence

containing a request is usually indicated in the Karakalpak language with the word “mu'mkin emes”.

This study approached the semantic and pragmatic functions of the modality category in English and Karakalpak under the umbrellas of modality and politeness. The analyses of modals as particular politeness strategies revealed that there is a close relation between politeness and modality. To be precise, politeness strategies in language communication can be examined through the analysis of modal verbs used in discourse material.

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